

Subsoil Characterization in Wudil, Kano for structure Erection and Water zones location Using VES Method

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Abstract:- Urban development and infrastructure construction require proper understanding of the subsurface geophysics and hydrogeology to ensure safe and sustainable construction practices. This research presented geoelectric investigation conducted, to characterize the subsoil and determine suitable sites for erecting building and borehole drilling in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano's premises. The geoelectric investigation involved the use of electrical resistivity method, which is a non-invasive geophysical technique that measures the electrical properties of the subsurface materials. The investigation utilized a combination of vertical electrical sounding (VES) and electrical profiling techniques to obtain subsurface resistivity data at the located site. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted using standard Geoelectric software and techniques to determine the subsurface characteristics, including the lithology, thickness, and water-bearing potential of the subsoil layers. The results revealed the presence of various subsurface formations, including clayey/silty, sandy, and the aquifer layer of the study area, with resistivity values ranging from low to high. Based on the geoelectric data, the suitable area for building erection and borehole drilling were identified. Areas with high resistivity values (77.2 – 1593 Ohms m) were interpreted as potential locations for erecting building due to the presence of stable and competent subsurface materials. Areas with low resistivity values were interpreted as potential locations for borehole drilling due to the presence of water-bearing formations.

Keywords: Subsoil, geoelectric, Vertical electrical sounding, lithology, Electrical resistivity,

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1.0 Introduction:

It is a common occurrence in Nigeria, cases of collapsed/distressed buildings. Contrary to the believe of the Nigerian Institute of Engineers (NISE) that assumes that the major cause of collapsed building is structural failure, there are many causes of this problem but the most fundamental cause is foundation failure. This foundation problem may be as a result of not using the right foundation type, using a weak soil strata that does not have the strength/capacity to carry the load on it (low bearing pressure). Most builders fail to recognize that the soil surrounding a foundation is responsible for the majority of foundation failures. Even foundations built with good materials and first class workmanship will fail if poor soil conditions were considered. Tomlinson, (1986)

Groundwater is the water that lies beneath the ground surface filling the pore spaces between grains in the bodies of sedimentary rocks (Joel, 2012). The availability of quality water resources has always been the primary concern of every community. Despite the abundance of rainfall, the problem of obtaining adequate quality water is generally becoming a problem due to the increase in population and industrialization. As a result of this, surface water

such as streams, hand dug wells and rivers cannot be dependable throughout the year, the need for other alternatives to supply water is necessary. Almost all formations will produce water, but those not capable of meeting even modest supply demands are called aquitards. Potable water is one of the major resources that a human being of any nation can benefit from (Alile et al, 2008). This is because water is a free gift of nature to mankind. The world is made to depend on the most reliable source of fresh water which lies beneath the earth surface known as groundwater. Therefore, subsoil characterization using geophysical methods helps to identify the lithology and soil strata with competent layers for erecting structures and soil profiling for water bearing zones. Parameters such as conductivity, porosity, permeability and transmissibility characterized groundwater and distinguished it from the surrounding media (Fristchnecht,1967, Foster and Grey, 1997). In this research, Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) using Schlumberger array will be adopted because of its high penetrating ability in locating groundwater aquifer (Keary et al., 2002) at the located site in the premises of Nigeria Police Academy (POLAC), Wudil, where constructions and borehole drillings are ongoing.

Fig 1 Map of Wudil local government locating POLAC

Figure 2 Located Area of Study in Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano

1.3 GEOLOGY AND HYDROGEOLOGY OF THE LOCATION

The formation consists of hard underrate ferruginous sandstone, grits, arkoses, breccia and basal conglomerate, lying unconformable on the basement complex of Nigeria. The upper part of the terrain is underlain by soft friable ferruginous Sandstone, arkoses, breccia and basal conglomerate of Ilo/Gundumi formation. There are two auriferous layers in this area, the soft friable and hard underrated ferruginous sandstone in the overburden

Figure 3 Materials used for Data collection at the located site

Methods:

The principal instrument used for this survey is the (Signal Averaging System, (SAS 300) Terrameter. The Schlumberger array method was used; the current

The location of the study area falls between Latitude $11^{\circ} 49' 54.0''N$ and $8^{\circ}48'19''N$ and Longitude $11^{\circ}37'01.6''E$ and $8^{\circ}36'06.2''E$ Wudil, Kano State.

of the basement complex. In the basement rocks, groundwater occurs either in the weathered mantle or in joints and fractured systems in the weathered/fresh rocks. The presence of ground water in any given area is therefore dependent upon whether sufficient thickness and lateral extent of weathered materials are present with high hydraulic characteristics to provide the reservoir or joint and fractures are available in the decomposed rocks (Saminu et al., 2018).The hydrogeological conditions found in Kano and noted that the groundwater is stored in the superficial weathered mantle derived from crystalline rocks of the Basement Complex which form an aquifer of poor quality (Saminu et al., 2018)

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials:

1. SAS 300 Terrameter
2. Single Core Cables
3. Stainless Steel Electrodes
4. Measuring tapes
5. 12volt Battery
6. Hammer
7. Gloves
8. GPS from a Mobile device

electrodes are spaced much further apart than the potential electrode. Schlumberger array data were acquired using SAS 300 Terrameter along with other accessories-cables, electrodes, pegs, ranging poles, hammers and measuring tape. The resistivity of the subsoil on the area of study were taken through the following procedure: Vertical Electrical

Soundings (VES) using Schlumberger array were carried out at eighteen (12) stations. A regular direction of N-S azimuth was maintained in the orientation of the profiles.

The measuring tape was used to measure the area of study. Each of the stainless steel electrode was pushed down into the ground with the hammer to a depth of about 0.2m.

The single core cables were used to connect to four of the electrodes to the SAS Terrameter, potential cables connected to P1 and P2 on the SAS terrameter and current cables connected to the C1 and C2 on the SAS Terrameter.

A 12volt battery was used to power the SAS terrameter and the current amplitude was set by the operator to suit the actual survey conditions. It can be set to 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 5.0, 10.0, and 20.0MH at 50V maximum current electrode potential.

Current injection: Current was injected into the soil using one of the electrodes, and the electrical potential difference

Figure 4 Schlumberger Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) Array (Keary et al., 2002)

3.0 RESULTS AND DIDCUSSION

VES data acquired were quantitatively interpreted using IPI 2 WIN software. The VES points identified four layers of the subsurface at the located site, which were the top soil, weathered basement, fractured basement and fresh basement. From the characteristics of resistivity of weathered and fractured basement layers of the VES points, these indicated that the weathered and the fractured basement are classified as auriferous layers where fresh ground water was expected to be in abundance. The resistivity of the sound curves of the VES points clearly identified the depth of the aquifer layer ranged between 10.8 to 57.8m. From the interpreted VES curves, it's clearly

is measured between two or more electrodes. This measurement was repeated for different frequencies to obtain a frequency response of the soil.

The resistance readings at every VES point were automatically displayed on the digital readout screen and it was recorded. After which the electrodes were moved to a different spacing.

The electrode were spaced at 1.0,1.5,2.5,3.5,5.0,7.5,10.0, 15.0,20.0,30.0 meters and the resistance readings displayed on the SAS terra-meter were also recorded

The data obtained from the measurements were processed using special software to obtain information about the electrical resistivity and conductivity of the soil. The data can be displayed as a resistivity profile or a conductivity profile, which provides information about the subsurface structure and soil properties.

shown that all the VES points have tendency of producing high yielding ground water via borehole drilling.

Also, the VES curves indicated that geoelectric section consisted of near surface layer that had highly variable resistivity ranging from about 77.2 – 1593ohms m. The difference in the resistivity values was due to the variations in the amount of grain size distribution of the formations. Areas with high resistivity values indicated the presence of gravel and sand as the top soil, which favours construction and erection of building and structures, while those with relatively low resistivity values indicated the presence of clay/clay with sand which usually contains the ground water aquifer. The thickness of the top soil layers varied in different parts of the location, however, it was estimated to be less than 3m. The resistivity values of VES 1-12, ranged between 15.9 – 1593 ohmsm, while the thickness was between 1.26 – 57.8m

Table1 VES Sounding Data

L(cm)	b(cm)	R(ohm)	K(m)	ρA
1.0	0.5	70.76	5.89	416.78
1.5	0.5	30.60	13.74	420.44
2.5	0.5	13.88	38.88	539.65
3.5	0.5	3.86	76.58	295.68
5.0	0.5	2.26	156.69	358.82
7.5	0.5	0.10	353.04	352.69
10	0.5	0.10	627.92	310.82
7.5	1.0	3.42	175.93	600.80
10.0	1.0	1.65	313.37	517.69
15.0	1.0	0.47	706.07	332.56
25.0	1.0	0.17	1962.71	329.56
35.0	1.0	0.13	3847.67	587.89
50.0	1.0	0.09	7853..20	698.93
75.0	1.0	0.05	17676.67	1024.10
100.0	1.0	0.02	3145.14	628.30

Figure 5 Interpreted Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES1)

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	735	2.61	2.61	-2.609
2	422	20.5	23.1	-23.12
3	109	34.7	57.8	-57.8
4	783			

Figure 6 Interpreted VES 2

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	605	1.69	1.69	-1.695
2	436	2.22	3.91	-3.91
3	117	50.2	54.1	-54.14
4	568			

Figure 7 Interpreted VES 3

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	499	2.03	2.03	-2.029
2	195	8.77	10.8	-10.8
3	310	12.9	23.7	-23.68
4	606			

Figure 8 Interpreted VES 4

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	167	1.63	1.63	-1.63
2	276	2.59	4.22	-4.224
3	121	6.58	10.8	-10.8
4	646			

Figure 9 Interpreted VES 5

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	167	1.63	1.63	-1.63
2	228	2.59	4.22	-4.224
3	121	6.58	10.8	-10.8
4	646			

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	1593	1.91	1.91	-1.909
2	216	2.13	4.04	-4.043
3	404	20.1	24.1	-24.1
4	3840			

VES

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	362	1.84	1.84	-1.84
2	105	1.26	3.1	-3.1
3	155	9.19	12.3	-12.29
4	553			

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	77.2	1.84	1.84	-1.84
2	15.9	1.26	3.1	-3.1
3	51	13.9	17	-16.99
4	155			

Figure 13 Interpreted VES 9

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	1138	1.47	1.47	-1.474
2	485	3.9	5.38	-5.376
3	168	24	29.4	-29.38
4	3287			

Figure 14 Interpreted VES 10

N	ρ	h	d	Alt
1	1138	2.06	2.06	-2.064
2	596	3.31	5.38	-5.376
3	206	31.1	36.5	-36.46
4	4484			

Figure 15 Interpreted VES 11

Figure 16 Interpreted VES 12

4.0 CONCLUSION

This study revealed that VES measurements are effective to evaluate the suitability of subsurface characterization to give insight to competent solid areas to erect buildings and locate potential ground water zones and conditions based on interpretation of VES data, hence, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The VES method is a non-destructive and appropriate technique to detect depth and thickness of various subsurface layers and the ground water zone within these layers in the study area.
2. The interpretation of the VES or the subsurface geoelectric layers showed different resistivity values in the location due to the type of formation. The curves are basically HK indicating four subsurface layers, their thickness, depth and water bearing capacity
3. The resistivity values varied from 15.9 to 1593 Ohms m and the thickness ranged between 1.26 – 57.8m
4. Areas with high resistivity values were interpreted as potential locations for erecting building due to the presence of stable and competent subsurface materials. Areas with low resistivity values were interpreted as potential locations for borehole drilling due to the presence of water-bearing formations.

5.0 Recommendation

It is recommended that induced polarization (IP) and seismic methods should be carried out within the study area in order to compliment and correlate the results of this work.

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